

Multi-recycling plutonium in fast molten chloride reactors: a methodology for fuel cycle simulation and its application to burner and breeder reactors.

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ABSTRACT

Plutonium is produced in important quantities by pressurized water reactor (PWR) fleet operation. As a result, fuel cycle strategies that make use of this plutonium have emerged. The French strategy aims at multi-recycling plutonium in its PWR fleet. Some long-term alternatives, relying on new reactor concepts, are deemed relevant for fuel cycle analysis. In particular, molten chloride fast reactors are considered for their potential flexible fuel cycle and their ability to burn or breed plutonium stockpiles. In this paper is presented a reactor core model for batch-operated molten salt reactors. This reactor model is then used within a simplified fuel cycle simulation code. Within this framework, behaviors of RAPTOR reactor, a burner concept, and CI-MSFR reactor, a breeder concept, are illustrated with respect to their influence on an initial plutonium stockpile. It is shown that those two concepts perform as expected: the RAPTOR reactor fleet manages to reduce the plutonium stockpile, and the CI-MSFR reactor fleet is able to increase the stockpile. Plutonium isotopic content in the stockpile converges in both cases. Then, some limitations are shown, notably that batch-operated molten salt reactor with a high reprocessing rate are quite sensitive to cooling time before reprocessing of the nuclear fuel. Finally, it is demonstrated that changing the reprocessing rate has a strong impact on breeding performance.

Keywords: molten salt reactor, plutonium multi-recycling, self-consumption of nuclear fuel

1. INTRODUCTION

Considerable amounts of plutonium is present in spent fuel as it builds up as a product of neutron capture on ^{238}U which is introduced in great quantity in fresh nuclear fuel. Some strategies take use of this plutonium as its quality as a fissile material makes it a credible alternative to low enriched uranium fuel in both Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) and Boiling Water Reactor (BWR). Plutonium quality is defined as the sum of mass fractions of odd numbered plutonium isotopes divided by the total plutonium mass fraction. The higher the quality, the higher the fissile content. Such a strategy is deployed at the industrial scale in the French nuclear fuel cycle, consisting of "mono-recycling" of plutonium from spent fuel of low enriched uranium assembly to make fresh fuel. This newly produced plutonium based fuel is called MOX, as it is a mix of plutonium and uranium oxides. The question of the use of plutonium from spent MOX fuels is an open matter at the International scale. The current French strategy aims to do multi-recycling of this plutonium in the EDF PWR fleet [1]. Plutonium from spent MOX fuel can be seen either as an asset to be consumed so as to extract a maximum of energy or as an asset to start a fleet of iso-generator reactors. The latter would function by regenerating the same amount of plutonium consumed within operation cycles by neutron capture on ^{238}U . Two paradigms exist for plutonium stock management. First is the burner strategy, whose purpose is to reduce plutonium stocks until there is not enough to fuel a single reactor. The second is the breeder

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strategy, which aims to convert as much fertile matter as possible (such as ^{238}U) into energy, maintaining a constant plutonium stock to operate a breeder reactor fleet. To fulfill this objective, both strategies must be able to recycle their own plutonium.

In this paper, the focus is given to molten salt reactor as a technology for multi-recycling of plutonium from spent MOX fuel. Reprocessing time is neglected which implies no product of plutonium decay is present in fresh fuel. Especially, the focus is directed towards molten chloride fast reactor as this technology presents three decisive advantages within the frame of the French strategy on nuclear fuel cycle:

- Molten chloride is compatible with hydro-metallurgical processes, enabling use of works on advanced separation of actinides [2],
- High solubility of actinides is considered feasible in molten chloride, thus enabling a flexible fuel management,
- Chloride element is less likely to thermalize the neutronic spectrum than fluoride.

We consider two molten chloride reactor designs for multi-recycling:

- RAPTOR design is a 300 MWth molten chloride reactor, with a fuel salt $\text{NaCl} - \text{MgCl}_2 - \text{PuCl}_3$. It is aimed at reducing the plutonium stockpiles. Its design has been established in [3].
- CI-MSFR design is a 3000 MWth molten chloride reactor with a fuel salt $\text{NaCl} - \text{UCl}_3 - \text{PuCl}_3$. Its goal is to be able to start up with any plutonium stockpile and breed its own fuel from ^{238}U introduced in the core [4]. Swerving from the reference design, we consider a blanket-less design of the CI-MSFR.

Both strategies are fundamentally opposed but they commonly share the need to characterize the effect of multi-recycling plutonium from spent fuel. Plutonium has to transit several times from reactor cores to nuclear fuel cycle facilities to be reprocessed.

2. METHOD

2.1. RAPTOR and CI-MSFR: Two Fast Chloride Molten Salt Reactors for Different Purposes

The MIMOSA European project [5] aims at studying the feasibility of a burner molten salt reactor. The reactor design is based on the RAPTOR design developed by Laura Mesthiviers in her PhD thesis [3]. This design is a loop-type molten salt reactor, with a critical core and pumps, heat exchangers and pipes closing the fuel circuit. Around the critical core there is a radial reflector in stainless steel and a neutronic absorbent made of boron carbide. Around the fuel circuit, radial and axial reflectors of stainless steel are positioned.

The volume of the fuel circuit is 4 m^3 , while the volume of the active core is 2 m^3 . The reference feed salt considered is a ternary $56.75\%\text{NaCl} - 2.25\%\text{MgCl}_2 - 32\%\text{PuCl}_3$, with plutonium reference isotopic content described in table I. This reference salt is computed so that, by reprocessing 0.0556 m^3 every three month of the fuel circuit and bringing in this fuel salt in place, the reactor is critical at equilibrium cycle. This reprocessing rate implies that the whole volume of the fuel circuit is reprocessed in 18 years.

The CI-MSFR reactor is a design developed by Hugo Pitois in his PhD thesis [4] within the frame of the European project SAMOSAFER. This design is also a loop-type reactor, with a total fuel circuit volume of 45.46 m^3 and a active core of 20 m^3 .

The reference feed salt considered is a ternary $64\%\text{NaCl} - 29.9375\%\text{UCl}_3 - 6.0625\%\text{PuCl}_3$, with plutonium reference isotopic content described in table I and uranium isotopic content corresponding to a depleted uranium with an enrichment in ^{235}U of 0.25 wt. %. This reference salt is computed so that, by reprocessing 4.566 m^3 every three month of the fuel circuit and bringing in this fuel salt in place, the

reactor is critical at equilibrium cycle. This reprocessing rate implies the whole volume of the core is reprocessed every two year and a half.

Low quality and high quality plutonium isotopic content are presented in Table II and in Table III, as fuel cycle simulations performed in Section 3 study the influence of plutonium isotopic content on a MSR fleet start-up.

Table I. Feed salt reference plutonium.

Isotopes	Mass fraction (wt. %)
^{238}Pu	4.21
^{239}Pu	38.17
^{240}Pu	32.44
^{241}Pu	12.47
^{242}Pu	12.71

Table II. Feed salt low quality plutonium.

Isotopes	Mass fraction (wt. %)
^{238}Pu	4.21
^{239}Pu	25.17
^{240}Pu	45.44
^{241}Pu	6.47
^{242}Pu	18.71

Table III. Feed salt high quality plutonium.

Isotopes	Mass fraction (wt. %)
^{238}Pu	3.21
^{239}Pu	43.17
^{240}Pu	30.44
^{241}Pu	16.47
^{242}Pu	6.71

2.2. In-evolution Hypotheses and Refueling Strategy

We define the reprocessing ratio τ_{RE} as the ratio between the volume reprocessed at each end of cycle V_{RE} and the volume of the full fuel circuit V_{fuel} . The reprocessing rate is given by $\tau_{RE} = \tau_{RE} / \Delta t$, where each cycle length Δt is the time of irradiation between two batch reprocessing steps.

The refueling strategy associated to those reactors are drastically different:

- for the Cl-MSFR the aim is to reprocess the fuel circuit relatively fast as it ensures the plutonium produced from operating the reactor is of a good quality ;
- for the RAPTOR reactor the aim is to incinerate plutonium and alleviate any stress on the refueling facilities by lowering the reprocessing rate as much as possible.

In both concepts, reactivity is tuned by varying PuCl_3 fraction in the feed salt. NaCl molar fraction remains fixed and the ternary salt serves as complement (MgCl_2 in the case of RAPTOR concept and UCl_3 for the Cl-MSFR concept). Table IV and table V sum up the main differences between the two designs as considered in this paper.

Table IV. RAPTOR concept main parameters and refueling options.

Thermal power (in MWth)	500
Average fuel circuit temperature (in K)	873
Cycle length Δt (in days)	91.3
Reprocessing ratio τ_{RE}	1.39 %

Table V. Cl-MSFR concept main parameters and refueling options.

Thermal power (in MWth)	3000
Average fuel circuit temperature (in K)	925
Cycle length Δt (in days)	91.3
Reprocessing ratio τ_{RE}	10.02 %

2.3. Direct Equilibrium Computation

In order to perform fuel cycle simulations with batch-wise reprocessed molten chloride designs, a reactor core model has to be established. This core model is built upon the *in-equilibrium* hypothesis: for a certain isotopic content of the reactor loading, it is supposed the reactor has reached its equilibrium state. As every reactor in the fleet is considered at equilibrium, the nuclear fuel transitioning from the reactor cores can be factorized: the global fluxes of plutonium is the product of the fluxes yielded by the *equilibrium model* for one reactor and the number of reactors installed. It is important to note the *equilibrium model* is dynamic as it adapts its evaluation of fluxes depending on the isotopic content of plutonium available in the fuel cycle.

This kind of model, practical in terms of computational power, is standard for PWR and SFR in the EDF R&D fuel cycle simulation code TIRELIRE-STRATEGIE [6]. We establish such a model for batch-wise reprocessed molten salt reactors (MSR) and apply it to a simple simulation study where a fleet of MSR is using an initial stockpile of plutonium.

It has been shown that direct equilibrium computation can be done for batch-wise reprocessed molten chloride reactors [7]. This fast computational scheme allows to constitute datasets where a predictive model can be trained. Two distinct predictive models are built:

- a first model \tilde{f} that computes the k_{eff} of the in-equilibrium core for a certain isotopic content and molar fraction of PuCl_3 ,
- a second model \tilde{g} that computes the uranium, plutonium and minor actinides inventories in the in-equilibrium core for a certain isotopic content and molar fraction of PuCl_3 .

For each new plutonium isotopic content, the model \tilde{f} is recursively called so as to compute the molar fraction $x(\text{PuCl}_3)$ in the feed salt to maintain the in-equilibrium core critical. Once the feed salt molar fraction of PuCl_3 is computed, the model \tilde{g} yields an estimation of the heavy nuclei inventory for the corresponding critical in-equilibrium core. This procedure is referred to as the *equilibrium model* in the following.

2.4. A Simplified Fuel Cycle Simulation Code

For the purpose of studying the effect of a fleet of MSR on a stockpile of plutonium, a dedicated fuel cycle simulation code has been developed. This fuel cycle simulation code relies on the MSR equilibrium model described in Section 2.3.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of one step within the simplified fuel cycle simulation code.

The aim of this code is to characterize the behavior of a MSR fleet on a initial plutonium stockpile. Once unloaded, cooled and reprocessed, plutonium is mixed with the main plutonium stockpile. In the studies presented in Section 3 and in Section 4, the time-step is fixed to 1 year. To ensure comparability across time steps, the stock is annualized: each simulation year is represented by a single loading–unloading cycle, corrected by a scaling factor equal to the ratio between the effective campaign length and the simulation time step. Moreover, all reloads occurring within a given time step are assumed to be identical. In addition, we assume perfect isolation of plutonium throughout the cycle, such that no material losses occur. The different operations performed within one step are presented in Figure 1.

3. REFLECTIONS ON REACTOR AND PLUTONIUM STOCKPILES

In order to evaluate performance of reactor models introduced in the previous Section 2.3, cooling time is considered null in Section 3. The analysis is restricted to the in-core consumption of plutonium and its impact on fuel quality. Within this framework, the study focuses on the temporal evolution of plutonium quality as the initial stockpile is depleted and recycled through the reactor fleet. This approach enables a systematic assessment of isotopic degradation mechanisms and provides insight into the long-term sustainability of plutonium-based fuel cycles under the modeling assumptions considered.

In Section 3, the initial plutonium stockpile amounts to 100 tons. Uranium stockpile is not studied as the quantity of depleted uranium is not judged limiting in the case of the deployment of an iso-breeding reactor fleet. The reactor fleet is started with a fixed installed capacity of 6 GW of thermal power.

3.1. Multi-recycling Plutonium in a MSR Fleet: Evolution of the Plutonium Stockpile

In this Section, the effect of a MSR fleet is studied on the initial plutonium stockpile with reference isotopic content described in Table I. The global plutonium inventory distribution (stockpile or in-core) is presented in Figure 2.

(a) Evolution of the plutonium isotopic content in the stockpile - burner scenario, no cooling.

(b) Evolution of the plutonium isotopic content in the stockpile - breeder scenario, no cooling.

Figure 2. Fuel cycle simulation results with reference initial plutonium content, both burner and breeder scenarios.

In RAPTOR burner fleet (Figure 2a), the global inventory decreases quickly: in 100 years, the 100 tons of plutonium are reduced to less than 3 tons, which corresponds to what is stored inside the last reactor in operation. As stockpile decreases, reactors are shut down so as to feed the remaining fleet. This effect is illustrated in Figure 2a. In CI-MSFR fleet, the simulation was developed over 300 years in order to capture efficiently the self consumption regime of a breeding reactor fleet.

The initial plutonium stockpile increases, as illustrated in Figure 2b. The breeder character of the reactor is thus confirmed, with an estimated production of plutonium per energy produced of 2.4 kg/TWh_{th} in the self consumption regime.

3.2. Multi-recycling Plutonium in a MSR Fleet: Impact of Initial Isotopic Content

The results developed in previous Section 3.1 are obtained with the reference initial plutonium content from Table I. It is proposed to study the quality of the plutonium in the stockpile where alternative burner and breeder scenarios are played out with initial isotopic content described in Table II and in Table III.

(a) Evolution of the plutonium quality in the stockpile - burner scenario, no cooling.

(b) Evolution of the plutonium quality in the stockpile - breeder scenario, no cooling.

Figure 3. Fuel cycle simulation results with different initial plutonium content, both burner and breeder scenarios.

It is illustrated in Figure 3 that the quality of plutonium in the stockpile converges regardless of initial quality. In that regard, both burner and breeder strategies show the same mechanism: the final quality of the plutonium stockpile is only governed by the reactor type deployed and their management. As the final quality is only dependent on reactor type and management deployed, it is referred to as the *self-consumption plutonium quality*. This convergence to *self-consumption quality* ensures the errors born from the *equilibrium model* do not stack up.

4. SENSITIVITY OF FUEL CYCLE SIMULATIONS TO THE REACTOR DESIGN AND ITS FUEL MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

In this Section it is proposed to perform some sensitivity studies on the fuel cycle simulations, notably the effect of cooling time on the mobilized plutonium per installed power and the impact of the reprocessing frequency on the plutonium stockpile.

4.1. Sensitivity of Fuel Cycle Simulations to Cooling Times

A parameter of importance is the cooling time t_{cool} , especially with respect to the time fuel spends in core t_{core} . It can be demonstrated that for a batch-wise reprocessed molten salt reactor, average time of residence of a compound in reactor core is $\langle t_{core} \rangle = \Delta t / \tau_{RE}$. It is shown in Figure 4 that the greater t_{cool} is relative to t_{core} , the more the mobilized mass of plutonium increases. Figure 4a and Figure 4b show that in-core mobilization builds up higher than the reference simulation, due to plutonium cooling degrading plutonium quality further. On the other hand, Figure 4c and Figure 4d show lesser sensitivity to plutonium degradation. Plutonium total mobilization increases faster in the case of the breeder

simulation, as $\langle t_{core} \rangle = 2.5$ years, while $\langle t_{core} \rangle = 14.3$ years in the case of the burner simulation. Peaks in the cooling mobilization of plutonium in Figure 4a and in Figure 4b are due to reactor unloading.

(a) Mobilized plutonium per installed thermal power - burner scenario, 2 year cooling.

(b) Mobilized plutonium per installed thermal power - burner scenario, 5 year cooling.

(c) Mobilized plutonium per installed thermal power - breeder scenario, 2 year cooling.

(d) Mobilized plutonium per installed thermal power - breeder scenario, 5 year cooling.

Figure 4. Fuel cycle simulation results for different cooling times, both burner and breeder scenarios.

In general, the total mobilized mass of plutonium per installed thermal power \tilde{m}_{cycle} can be expressed knowing the in-core mobilized mass of plutonium per installed thermal power \tilde{m}_{core} :

$$\tilde{m}_{cycle} \propto \frac{\langle t_{core} \rangle + t_{cool}}{\langle t_{core} \rangle} \tilde{m}_{core} .$$

4.2. Sensitivity of Fuel Cycle Simulations to Reprocessing Rates

To alleviate shortcomings illustrated in the previous Section, especially sensitivity of \tilde{m}_{cycle} with increasing cooling times, it is proposed to change the reprocessing frequency of the CI-MSFR reactor so that $\langle t_{core} \rangle = 6$ years. Results presented below in Figure 5 are obtained with the reference simulation parameters detailed in Section 3, using the modified CI-MSFR core model. As observed in Figure 5b, decreasing the reprocessing rate of the CI-MSFR reactor changes drastically the breeding character of the reactor. In that case, the CI-MSFR reactor is a net consumer of plutonium (≈ 5.7 kg/TWh_{th}): there is a trade-off between in-core breeding and mobilized plutonium mass per installed thermal power.

(a) Evolution of the plutonium quality in the stockpile.

(b) Evolution of masses of plutonium in reactor core and in stockpile.

Figure 5. Fuel cycle simulation results for the breeder scenario with a decreased reprocessing rate.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a model for fuel cycle simulation of batch-operated molten salt reactors is investigated. It is shown especially that both burner and breeder strategies are possible with molten chloride reactors RAPTOR and CI-MSFR. Burner strategies require reactors functioning for a significant extent with low quality plutonium, therefore those reactors should be designed in advance with this technical requirement. For breeder strategies, it is observed that production of plutonium per thermal energy varies significantly with feed salt isotopic content of plutonium, thus it is recommended that breeder reactor performance assessment is made with self-consumption isotopic content. Lastly, cooling time is a major issue for reactors where the time of residence in-core is similar to the cooling time, as the plutonium mobilization limits the number of reactors that can be deployed: fertile blanket introduction remains crucial for molten chloride breeder reactors.

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